

IMPORTANCE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN PEDAGOGY

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of modern technologies in the work of a pedagogue, and it is explained with the help of the necessary literature.

Keywords: pedagogue, technology, student, time, economy, education, science, education, future, people.

Speaking of pedagogy, when did the science of pedagogy appear? We need to talk directly about its importance in people's lives.

Pedagogy (from Greek paidagogike, paidagogos “child” and “to lead”) is a science that studies the general laws of social education, the essence and problems of educating the young generation in accordance with a single social goal in a particular society. Pedagogy is a science that belongs to the system of social sciences and studies the problems of raising and educating the young generation and adults based on the ideas of national independence.

Didactics (theory of education) and the theory of education are important components of the science, as the science of pedagogy focuses on two important aspects of personality development – its teaching and upbringing.

Well, we got acquainted with a brief definition of pedagogy. But what are the characteristics of the dependence of pedagogy on technology?

Pedagogical technology – studies the problems of using modern pedagogical technologies in the process of education and training, increasing the

effectiveness of the process of education and training based on the technological approach.

As we step on the path of building a modern state based on a developed market economy and ensure a consistent transition from a strong state to a strong civil society, only those who deeply understand the need for the harmony of national and universal values, have modern knowledge, intellectual potential and We have always imagined that only people who possess advanced technologies can achieve the goals of strategic development set before us” [2].

First, let’s clarify the concept of “technology”. This word entered the science in 1872 in connection with technical progress and comes from two Greek words – “technos” (techne) – art, skill, craft and “logos” (logos) – science. It means “craft science”. However, even this expression cannot fully describe the modern technological process. The technological process provides for the execution of operations in a certain sequence, always using the necessary tools and conditions. To be more precise, a technological process is the activity of a worker (working machine) to create a product as a result of gradual impact on labor objects (raw materials) with labor tools. If we turn this definition to the topic of research, that is: Pedagogical technology is the influence of the teacher (educator) on students (students) in certain conditions with the help of educational tools. And as a product of this activity, it is the process of forming predetermined personal qualities in them.

As can be seen from the definition given above, the technological process was taken as the basis for explaining the concept of pedagogical technology. In fact, there are many definitions of this concept in pedagogical literature. In the pedagogical literature, one can find various forms of the term “technology”: “teaching technology”, “educational technology”, “information technology”, “educational process technology”, etc. Although teaching technology is a concept close to pedagogical technology, it does not mean exactly the same, because it

expresses the way of mastering specific educational material within a certain subject, topic and questions around a certain technology. . It stands in line with more private methods.

Pedagogical technology represents the tactics of introducing information technology and is built on the basis of knowledge related to the laws of the functional system of “teacher-pedagogical process-pupil (student)”.

It should be noted separately that at the same time there is no single opinion on the logical-ideological interpretation of the concept of educational technology. More than 300 definitions are given in pedagogical literature.

As mentioned above, although the theory of pedagogical technology has been based since the second half of the last century, there are different approaches to the concept of “pedagogical technology”. In particular, the pedagogic scientist V.P. Bospalko defines the pedagogical technology as “the project of a specific pedagogical system applied in practice” and focuses on the preliminary design of the educational and pedagogical process. And N.F. Talzina notes that pedagogical technology should be “an independent science that develops methods promoting certain principles between science and practice, and is directed to solving issues such as their consistent application”, etc.[3].

Technology (Greek: “techno” – craft, master and “logos” – science, education) – methods of turning raw materials into finished products based on scientific practice.

Technology (Greek techne – art, skill, learning) is a system that regulates the methods of obtaining, processing and processing products in industry, construction, transport, agriculture and other fields; science dealing with the development, implementation and improvement of these methods. Each industry has its own technology: mining technology, mechanical engineering technology, construction technology, agriculture, etc.[2].

As we live and create in today’s time, it is difficult to imagine our activities

without modern technologies. For example, it is easier and more convenient to convey the internal structure of ordinary animals to students through color images than to explain them through black-and-white pictures. What if we convey the internal structure of this animal not only through color images, but also through short videos. If we take the beginning of the 20th century as an example, then technology was less developed than today. Thanks to the 21st century, it is an easy and convenient time for us to achieve high level of success in almost all fields. Because, for example, students previously had to wait in line for hours in libraries in order to read a book and acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. But thanks to today's technology, they can use electronic versions of these books in an easy and convenient way.

O'zbekiston Respublikasining birinchi prezidenti “ Zamonaviy ta' lim-tarbiya tizimini isloh qilish, zamon talablariga mos kadrlar tayyorlash ishini yo'lga qo'yish faoliyatimizning bosh yo'nalishi bo'lmog'i darkor” – ekanligini alohida qayd qilib o'tgan. Shuning uchun O'zbekiston Respublikasi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotini amalga oshirish borasida hal etilishi lozim bo'lgan ustuvor vazifalarni talab darajasida bajarish jadal rivojlantirishga katta ahamiyat berilishi lozim bo'ladi. Bu jarayon mamlakatimizning jahon bozorlarida o'ziga munosib o'ringa ega bo'lishi uchun ilm -fan yutuqlaridan va innovatsion texnologiyalardan keng ko'lamda foydalana oladigan malakali kadrlar tayyorlashni yo'lga qo'yish vazifalarini hal etish bilan uzviy bog'liqdir. Bu borada Prezident I.A .K arimov o'zining “O'zbekiston buyuk kelajak sari” asarida ta'kidlaganidek: “O'zbekiston innovatsion rivojlanish turining hozirgi zamon modeliga o'tish uchun hamma zarur sharoitlarga ega. Bu model vujudga keltirilgan ilmiy-texnikavi salohiyatdan keng va samarali foydalanishga, fundamental va amaliy fanning yutuqlarini, chuqur ilm talab qiladigan texnologiyalarni amaliyotga keng joriy etishga, yuqori malakali, iqtidorli ilmiy kadrlar sonini ko'paytirishga asoslanadi. Bu – mamlakatimiz jahondagi

iqtisodiyoti va sanoati rivojlangan davlatlar qatoriga kirib borishining zarur sharti va mustahkam poydevori bo'lib xizmat qiladi"[1;3- bet].

If we look back at our past years and summarize them, we will understand the glory of our independence more deeply. We are experiencing a period of complete renewal in education, a literal transition to a new process and adaptation to it. If the Law “On Education” and the “National Program of Personnel Training” allowed us to abandon the old methods and reconstruct every aspect of education, “Development of School Education in 2004-2009 State Nationwide program” has widely revealed the opportunities gained: improved state education standards, educational programs, state requirements, new textbooks in modern classrooms, fully equipped schools.

Modern lessons are necessary to kindle the embers in the student’s heart, develop it in every way, and lead it from knowledge to knowledge.

Currently, the terms pedagogical technologies, educational technology, teaching technology are often mentioned in the science of pedagogy. To date, the concepts of “new pedagogical technology”, “advanced pedagogical technology”, “modern educational technology” in pedagogical literature, reports on educational problems, and official documents have not been standardized, as explained in encyclopedias. Q, a single interpretation of its meaning has not been developed, and therefore there are many different definitions of the phrase. Q, a single interpretation of its meaning has not been developed, and therefore there are many different definitions of the phrase.

The main idea behind education is to form personal qualities such as being tolerant, satisfied, respecting the opinion of others, national-cultural and universal values, abandoning the authoritarian and false way of thinking, realizing the unity of nature and man. Is considered humanitarian. The solution to this problem is to some extent related to the technologicalization of education.

“Technology is biotechnology from conditions of changing the shape, size,

properties, and tone of materials, raw materials, or certain products used in industrial processes for product production” [2].

Above, we have listed the positive aspects of modern technologies, i.e. their achievements, but the saying “There is another side of the coin” in our people is not for nothing. Today’s 21st century technologies are used differently by everyone. For example, students spend a lot of time on communication technology information that has absolutely nothing to do with education and upbringing. For example, mobile phones, some junk sites on the internet, DVD movies and some other pieces of technology like that. In these aspects, the task of teaching the wise use of these tools is the responsibility of parents and pedagogues.

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